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Phase coherence of cochlear microphonic potentials in cochlear implant users with ipsilateral residual hearing

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ABSTRACT:

Intracochlear recorded growth functions of cochlear potentials evoked by acoustic tones were analyzed by their phase coherence, variance, and density distribution. Potentials obtained from electrocochleography recorded in cochlear implant users with ipsilateral residual hearing were analyzed in the complex domain. The study shows that (1) the phase of the cochlear microphonic (CM) is coherent across stimulation levels, (2) CM potentials are circularly symmetric normally distributed in the complex domain, regardless of stimulation level or response amplitude, and (3) the variance of CM potentials remains consistent, irrespective of stimulation level. Based on these findings, we introduce a method that utilizes the phase coherence across stimulation levels to improve the accuracy of CM amplitude estimates, particularly when amplitudes are close to the noise floor. A key aspect of this method is addressing the bias introduced by the circularly symmetric normal distribution of additive Gaussian noise in the complex domain, which can lead to overestimation of signal magnitude. The results show that phase coherence can be used to enhance the accuracy of amplitude estimates of cochlear potentials, thereby making the recording process more efficient. Furthermore, the consistent variance of cochlear potentials enables noise estimations from recordings containing receptor potentials, independent of the stimulation level.

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I. INTRODUCTION

A cochlear implant (CI) is a neuroprosthetic device used to treat hearing loss when conventional hearing devices, such as hearing aids, are insufficient. CIs elicit auditory perception, enabling speech understanding through electrical stimulation of the auditory nerve [e.g., Loizou (1998) and Wouters *et al.* (2015)]. Several studies have demonstrated that combined electric-acoustic stimulation (EAS) offers advantages over both acoustic stimulation (AS) alone and electric stimulation (ES) alone [e.g., Büchner *et al.* (2009), Gifford *et al.* (2013), and Krüger *et al.* (2022)]. Advances in CI technology and surgical techniques [e.g., Hochmair *et al.* (2015), Lenarz *et al.* (2009), and von Ilberg *et al.* (1999)] allow the preservation of substantial low-frequency residual hearing during and after implantation (Frayssé *et al.*, 2006; James *et al.*, 2005; Kiefer *et al.*, 2005; von Ilberg *et al.*, 2011) and have broadened the criteria for implantation to include patients with substantial residual hearing (Kiefer *et al.*, 2005; Skarzynski and Lorens, 2010; von Ilberg *et al.*, 2011). As a result, the number of CI recipients with substantial residual hearing has increased in recent

years. Consequently, monitoring residual hearing in CI treatment is of utmost importance.

CIs designed for electrical stimulation have evolved considerably over time. Current CIs provide telemetry capabilities that enable the recording of auditory evoked potentials. The recording of electrophysiological potentials via CIs holds significant promise for both clinical and research applications. This technique offers the possibility of an objective evaluation of cochlear activity and thus of assessing the functionality of the peripheral auditory system without the additional effort of using external or transtympanic electrodes [e.g., Abbas *et al.* (2017), Koka *et al.* (2017a), Koka *et al.* (2017b), Koka and Litvak (2017), and Krüger *et al.* (2020b,a)].

Electrocochleography (ECoChG) has been used as a tool to objectively monitor the hearing function of CI recipients both during and after implantation [e.g., Bester *et al.* (2025), Haumann *et al.* (2025), Haumann *et al.* (2024), Haumann *et al.* (2019), Süntinger *et al.* (2022), Dalbert *et al.* (2015a), Dalbert *et al.* (2015b), Campbell *et al.* (2016), O’Leary *et al.* (2023), Buechner *et al.* (2022), and Saoji *et al.* (2023)]. ECoChG can support the prediction of hearing outcomes (Canfarotta *et al.*, 2021; Fitzpatrick *et al.*, 2014; Formeister *et al.*, 2015; McClellan *et al.*, 2014) and help determine the optimal setting of the CI or EAS system

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for hearing performance. Additionally, ECochG enables the tracking of changes in residual hearing over time (Abbas *et al.*, 2017; Kim *et al.*, 2018), which could be used to provide indications for interventions (Bester *et al.*, 2022) to adjust the CI and EAS fitting accordingly.

ECochG involves recording of potentials generated by the cochlear hair cells and the auditory nerve. In this process, evoked potentials caused by hair cell and nerve responses are recorded as a gross response consisting of four major potentials: the cochlear-microphonic potential (CM), the auditory nerve neurophonic potential (ANN), the compound action potential (CAP), and the summing potential (SP). The CM is a potential generated by the transducer current of the cochlear hair cells that follows the excitation stimulus. The ANN is the alternating proportion of the potential evoked by the auditory nerve. It is caused by phase locking of nerve responses to low-frequency (up to approximately 2 kHz) stimulation. The CAP results from synchronized nerve firing usually in response to fast-rising stimulus onsets. The SP results from the superposition of DC components of hair cell and nerve responses. It can appear as a baseline shift of the cochlear potentials in the course of stimulation.

Several studies have shown that monitoring the CM amplitude during electrode insertion can be helpful in preserving residual hearing during cochlear implantation (Dalbert *et al.*, 2015b; O'Leary *et al.*, 2023). For example, it was observed that drops in CM amplitude during electrode insertion correlate with poorer hearing preservation, compared to cases where the amplitude remains stable throughout the insertion (Dalbert *et al.*, 2015b; O'Leary *et al.*, 2023). In addition, it has been shown that surgical intervention triggered when CM amplitude dropped by at least 30% of a prior maximum amplitude during cochlear implantation resulted in significantly better hearing preservation in comparison to a control group (Bester *et al.*, 2022). Incorporating CM potential phase information into intraoperative monitoring can help distinguish whether observed changes in CM amplitude are due to the electrode contacting and potentially damaging the basilar membrane, or due to the electrode surpassing the CM potential generator (Buechner *et al.*, 2022; Saoji *et al.*, 2023). This may facilitate more precise and safer CI surgeries (Buechner *et al.*, 2022; Saoji *et al.*, 2023).

Intracochlear ECochG, derived via intracochlear electrodes of the CI, has been used to monitor changes in hair cell and auditory nerve potentials in response to AS. ECochG has also been utilized to objectively characterize the impact of ES on acoustic hearing (Krüger *et al.*, 2020a,b). Prior research has demonstrated that ECochG can be used to assess cochlear functionality during and following implantation [e.g., Suntinger *et al.* (2022), Dalbert *et al.* (2015a), and Dalbert *et al.* (2015b)]. Moreover, CM amplitude derived via intracochlear ECochG was used to predict behavioral hearing thresholds (Koka *et al.*, 2017a; Soulby *et al.*, 2021).

In clinical application and for the fundamental understanding of the auditory system, electrophysiological cochlear potential recording is promising for its objective, efficient measurements that do not require patient response. The small amplitudes of cochlear potentials and the limitations of current CI telemetry technology make high-quality auditory potential recording challenging. Particularly when determining electrophysiological thresholds or measuring potentials at psychoacoustic detection thresholds, an accurate measurement of the stimulus responses is limited by the further diminished magnitude of receptor potentials [e.g., Abbas *et al.* (2017), Koka *et al.* (2017a), Koka *et al.* (2017b), Koka and Litvak (2017), and Krüger *et al.* (2020a)].

The accuracy of recording cochlear potentials at low stimulation levels is constrained by the noise inherent to the measurements. Noise can be attenuated through the application of signal averaging, which entails the temporal averaging of multiple recordings of electrophysiological responses elicited by an identical stimulus. The improvement in signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) achieved through signal averaging is proportional to the square root of the total number of individual records averaged. Despite this, the feasible number of measurement repetitions, whether in a clinical setting or within the scope of scientific research, is inherently limited due to considerations of time efficiency and patient comfort.

The characterization of intracochlear recorded phase-intensity functions may provide insights about the contribution of sources generating these potentials, the electrode location, or the cochlear functionality of EAS users. However, detailed intracochlear CM response phase-intensity functions have yet to be investigated in humans. Extracochlear measurements have been made by Zhang (2013), who reported a trend for a phase difference comparing CM responses obtained for acoustic stimuli presented at 60 dB nHL (decibels normalized hearing level) and at 20 dB nHL. This is consistent with previous extracochlear measurements of CM potentials performed by Picton *et al.* (1977). In their study, a phase delay of 0.36 ms was observed in responses elicited by stimuli presented at 60 and 30 dB SL, using surface electrodes. Picton *et al.* (1977) argued that for low-intensities, there is a greater contribution of apical generated CMs which explains the observed phase shift. The behavior of the phase in CM recordings is complex, as it can be impacted by several factors such as the location of the recording electrode, the stimulus frequency, and the subject's hearing loss [e.g., Tejani *et al.* (2019), Abbas *et al.* (2017), Campbell *et al.* (2017), Eggermont (1979), and Zhang (2012)].

The present study deals with the analysis of intracochlear CM potentials recorded by Krüger *et al.* (2020a). These potentials were derived as the stimulus-following potential from recorded gross responses. For this, cochlear potentials were recorded in response to acoustic tone bursts presented with alternating polarities (condensation and rarefaction). It is assumed that the CM predominantly contributes to the first harmonic observed in the stimulus response,

due to its phase locking. Therefore, the difference potential obtained from ECoChG recordings in response to condensation and rarefaction stimulation is used to emphasize the CM. It should be noted that, due to the phase locking of the ANN to low-frequency stimuli with this method, the CM cannot be completely isolated [e.g., Fontenot *et al.* (2017) and Forgues *et al.* (2014)]. To avoid potential misunderstandings, the term CM_{h1} is used in the following for the potential derived from the first harmonic of the cochlear gross response.

In the current study, we characterize the phase of CM potentials (specifically CM_{h1}) in response to acoustic pure tone stimuli as a function of the stimulation level. For this, ECoChG recordings conducted by Krüger *et al.* (2020a) were analyzed. The current study demonstrates a phase coherence of CM potentials for various stimulation levels across subjects, as well as for individual subjects. Based on these findings, we introduce a method that utilizes the phase coherence to increase the accuracy of CM amplitude estimates, especially if these amplitudes are close to the noise floor. A key aspect of our method is addressing the bias in amplitude estimation introduced by taking the absolute value of samples from a circularly symmetric complex Gaussian distribution, which represents additive noise in the complex domain. This operation results in an overestimation of the signal's true magnitude. By recognizing and addressing this bias, we can significantly improve the accuracy of amplitude estimates ($p = 0.002$). When the phase of the signal is known, the component orthogonal to the phase axis in the complex domain can be identified as noise and excluded from the analysis. This approach is particularly beneficial in scenarios where the phase is known from measurements with improved SNR, achieved through more intense stimulation or longer averaging. Our method, therefore, provides a more precise estimation of CM amplitudes, enhancing the accuracy of the measurements even when the amplitudes are near the noise floor.

II. METHODS

A. ECoChG recordings

ECoChG growth functions analyzed in this study were obtained from recordings conducted by Krüger *et al.* (2020a), which obtained ECoChG recordings in ten subjects implanted with an Ultra HiFocus implant and a SlimJ electrode array. Figure 1 shows unaided air conduction pure tone thresholds of the study participants measured at the study appointment, as described in Krüger *et al.* (2020a). Table I shows demographic data of the ten subjects. The last column of Table I shows the corresponding audiometric frequencies used to evoke the recorded CM growth for each subject Krüger *et al.* (2020a).

The ECoChG recordings were derived through the most apical intracochlear CI electrode as the recording electrode, the implant's ring electrode as the reference electrode, and the case of the implant as the ground electrode. ECoChG growth was measured in response to 50 ms acoustic pure

tone stimuli, presented at various stimulation levels from most comfortable level (MCL) to below psychoacoustic detection thresholds. Each ECoChG measurement consisted of 120 epochs, presented with alternating polarities (120 condensation and 120 rarefaction).

A *post hoc* analysis based on the interquartile range (IQR) of the root mean square (RMS) amplitudes was conducted to exclude epochs from the ECoChG measurement that were contaminated by movement, myogenic, and non-neural artifacts (Simpson *et al.*, 2020). According to Goodman *et al.* (2024), Goodman *et al.* (2023), and Goodman *et al.* (2009), RMS amplitudes exceeding the third quartile plus 1.5 times the IQR were identified as artifacts and excluded from subsequent analyses. A total of 113 out of 7560 recorded epochs were rejected as artifacts. The percentage of rejections in individual ECoChG measurements ranged from 0% to 9.17%. On average, the rejection rate across all ECoChG measurements was 1.49% (or 1.8 epochs).

The recorded time series were averaged and the difference response (the difference between condensation and rarefaction) was calculated to determine the CM_{h1} potential. In addition to the averaged recordings, individual recordings were analyzed for a more detailed evaluation of CM_{h1} responses. Amplitudes and phases were determined by transforming the time series into the frequency domain using a discrete Fourier transform (DFT) of 404 samples, with zero-padding applied to improve estimation, following the procedure described in Krüger *et al.* (2020a).

FIG. 1. Unaided air conduction pure tone thresholds of all subjects (Krüger *et al.*, 2020a). The thresholds were measured via headphones (HDA 200, Sennheiser electronic GmbH & Co. KG, Wedemark, Germany) and a clinical audiometer (Audio 4000, Homoth Medizintechnik GmbH & Co. KG, Kaltenkirchen, Germany). The thresholds are given in dB HL according to DIN ISO 389-8:2004.

TABLE I. Demographic data of the subjects (Krüger *et al.*, 2020a).

ID	Gender	Age [years]	CI experience [days]	Etiology of deafness	Electrode type	Side	Frequency [Hz]
1	Male	53	231	Sudden hearing loss	Slim J	right	250
2	Female	48	77	Usher-syndrome	Slim J	right	500
3	Male	54	117	Idiopathic	Slim J	left	750
4	Female	34	80	Idiopathic	Slim J	left	250
5	Male	77	91	Idiopathic	Slim J	left	750
6	Female	70	83	Idiopathic	Slim J	left	500
7	Female	48	55	Traumatic	Slim J	right	250
8	Female	39	113	Idiopathic	Slim J	right	250
9	Male	52	55	Usher-syndrome	Slim J	left	500
10	Female	45	55	Cogan-I-syndrome	Slim J	left	750

B. Amplitude estimation using phase coherence

In this study, we introduce a method that utilizes the phase coherence of intracochlearly recorded potentials across stimulation levels to reduce the bias in estimating the amplitudes of CM_{h1} potentials in response to lower-intensity AS. The method we propose utilizes phase coherence and the circularly symmetric normal distribution of the recorded potentials in the complex domain, both of which are demonstrated in the Results section. In this context, a circularly symmetric normal distribution is a complex normal distribution in which the real and imaginary parts of the recorded potentials in the complex domain are normally distributed with equal variance. Its probability density function remains invariant when rotated around the origin. To enhance the amplitude estimation accuracy, phase information obtained with high SNR is used as a reference to determine the amplitudes of CM_{h1} potentials for soft stimulation levels. High SNR CM_{h1} phase can be obtained, for example, by recording CM_{h1} potentials in response to high stimulation levels (high SNRs) or through extensive averaging of multiple CM_{h1} recordings. The reference phase (ϕ_{ref}) can be determined, for example, directly from potentials recorded in response to high stimulation levels by computing the arctan of the ratio between the imaginary and real parts of the complex coefficients obtained from a DFT. For responses recorded at various stimulation levels, the phase can be determined by calculating the angle of the first principal component from a principal component analysis (PCA) of the potentials in the complex domain. Assuming phase coherence across stimulation levels, the phase of the CM potential is determined with higher accuracy from response recordings with good SNR (e.g., high stimulation levels). The reference phase is subsequently utilized to improve the amplitude determination of potentials at low stimulation levels and SNRs. For this, the amplitude of the $CM_{h1,n}$ response is calculated as the absolute value of I_n that is the projection of z_n onto the line defined by the reference phase ϕ_{ref} . This projection and the use of the absolute value is called folding. This process transforms the data's distribution from a normal distribution to a folded normal distribution, according to Eq. (4). Here, n is the index of the respective ECoChG epoch for which CM_{h1} is to be determined. It is calculated according to

Eq. (1), where $|z_n|$ is the absolute value and ϕ_{z_n} is the phase angle of the complex Fourier coefficient of an individual $CM_{h1,n}$ response and ϕ_{ref} is the reference phase angle. In this context, i represents the imaginary unit, which is used in the complex exponential term ($e^{i\phi_{ref}}$) to adjust the phase of the resulting amplitude,

$$I_n = |z_n| \cdot \cos(\phi_{z_n} - \phi_{ref}) \cdot e^{i\phi_{ref}}. \tag{1}$$

Alternatively, for an efficient implementation, the coordinate system can be rotated in the complex domain with respect to the reference phase. This allows the amplitude to be determined as the absolute value of the real part of the complex Fourier coefficient corresponding to the stimulus frequency. Equation (2) shows how this rotation can be applied. Here, $X[k]$ is the k -th component of the frequency spectrum. k can be set to correspond with the first harmonic of the CM response, $\chi[n]$ is the n -th value of the input sequence, N is the number of samples in the DFT, and i is the imaginary unit,

$$X[k] = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} \chi[n] \cdot e^{-i[(2\pi/N)kn - \phi_{ref}]}. \tag{2}$$

The improvement in amplitude determination of the recorded intracochlear potentials, achieved by utilizing their phase coherence across stimulation levels, can be explained by the underlying probability distribution and the way in which it is analyzed.

The variability in ECoChG measurements caused by additive normally distributed noise results in a circularly symmetric normal distribution of the complex Fourier coefficients of CM_{h1} responses.

The probability distribution of the magnitude of an underlying circularly symmetric normal distributed random variable, results in the Rician distribution according to Eq. (3),

$$f(x; \nu, \sigma) = \frac{x}{\sigma^2} e^{-\left(\frac{x^2 + \nu^2}{2\sigma^2}\right)} I_0\left(\frac{x\nu}{\sigma^2}\right), \tag{3}$$

where x is the magnitude of the circularly symmetric normal random vector, ν is the magnitude of the mean of the

underlying circularly symmetric normal distribution, σ is the scale parameter of the distribution [the standard deviation (STD) of the underlying circularly symmetric normal distribution], and I_0 is the modified Bessel function of the first kind with order zero.

In contrast, the determination of the magnitude of complex Fourier coefficients with respect to a specific phase, results in a folded normal distribution according to Eq. (4),

$$f(x; \mu, \sigma) = \frac{1}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} \left(e^{-(x-\mu)^2/2\sigma^2} + e^{-(x+\mu)^2/2\sigma^2} \right), \quad (4)$$

where μ is the mean and σ^2 is the variance of a normally distributed random variable x .

To illustrate the differences between the two methods, Fig. 2 shows the probability density functions of the CM_{h1} amplitudes, as defined by the Rician distribution (blue) and the folded normal distribution (red), based on Eqs. (3) and (4), respectively. The probability density functions for five stimulus response amplitudes ($\mu = 0, 0.5, 1, 1.5,$ and 5) of the underlying complex normal random value are shown. The expected values for both distributions were obtained via Monte Carlo simulations. Insert plots in Fig. 2 illustrate the circularly symmetric normal distribution for complex Fourier coefficients as obtained from CM_{h1} responses for the same five stimulus response amplitudes. For $\mu \gg \sigma$ it can be observed that the Rice and the folded normal distribution approximate the normal distribution. Consequently, differences in the expected values obtained from the two distributions are negligibly small. However, with a reduction of μ (for instance, when $\mu \leq \sigma$), the difference increases. This is because the estimation of the absolute amplitude is constrained by the magnitude of the STD (noise floor). In contrast, estimates obtained using additional phase information enable amplitude estimates below this noise floor.

Monte Carlo simulations were performed to compare amplitude estimates of the CM_{h1} response based on the Rice distribution and the folded normal distribution (Fig. 9). The left panel of Fig. 3 shows the expected values of the Rice distribution and the folded normal distribution as a function of the stimulus response amplitude (μV). The amplitude

shown on the x axis represents the center of the underlying complex normal distribution with a STD of 1. The middle panel of Fig. 9 shows the error of these estimates, which is the difference between the expected values and the amplitude (μV), for the Rice and the folded normal distribution. The right panel of Fig. 3 shows the difference (ΔE) between amplitude estimates based on the Rice distribution and the folded normal distribution as a function of the stimulus response amplitude for various STDs of the underlying complex normal distribution (σ).

C. Residual noise and noise floor measurements

The presence of constant noise in ECoG recordings, independent of stimulation levels or response amplitudes, allows estimations of residual noise (RN) and noise floor (NF) and avoids the need for additional measurements for characterization. The RN refers to the background interference in a measurement when a signal or electrophysiological response is present. The NF, on the other hand, represents the baseline level in a measurement when no signal or electrophysiological response is present. The RN can be determined as the standard error of the complex CM_{h1} response. This can be derived from the standard error of the underlying normally distributed real and imaginary parts of the CM_{h1} response epochs [Eq. (5)],

$$RN = \frac{\sqrt{\frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2}}{\sqrt{n}} = \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{n}}. \quad (5)$$

In Eq. (5), n is the number of epochs, x_i is the value of the i -th epoch, \bar{x} is the mean value of all epochs, and σ is the STD of the underlying normally distributed complex CM_{h1} response. The STD σ can be calculated as the STD of the real or the imaginary part of the complex numbers, or as the average of both.

The noise floor can be calculated using the residual noise estimation. In the case of using absolute amplitude, the noise floor NF_{Rice} [Eq. (6)] results from the expected value of the Rice distribution (Rayleigh distribution) with

FIG. 2. Circularly symmetric normal distribution and probability density functions for complex Fourier coefficients obtained from (CM_{h1}) responses. The probability density functions are derived from a Rician distribution (blue) and a folded normal distribution (red) for five stimulus response amplitudes ($\mu = 0, 0.5, 1, 1.5,$ and 5) of an underlying complex normal random variable with a STD of 1. The insets illustrate the circularly symmetric normal distribution for complex Fourier coefficients obtained from (CM_{h1}) responses for the same expected values. The density of the normal distribution is color-coded from yellow (high density) to purple (low density).

FIG. 3. Monte Carlo simulations comparing amplitude estimates (μV) of the simulated CM_{h1} response based on the Rice distribution and the folded normal distribution. The left panel shows the expected values of both distributions as a function of the stimulus response amplitude, with the amplitude on the x axis representing the center of the underlying complex normal distribution ($\text{STD} = 1$). The middle panel displays the error of these estimates, defined as the difference between the expected values and the amplitude. The right panel illustrates the difference (ΔE) between amplitude estimates from the Rice distribution and the folded normal distribution across various STDs (σ) of the underlying complex normal distribution.

the mean of the underlying random variable being 0 [Eq. (3)],

$$NF_{Rice} = RN \cdot \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2}}. \tag{6}$$

Considering the phase of the measured ECoChG, the noise floor $NF_{FoldedNormal}$ [Eq. (7)] can be calculated as the expected value of a folded normal distribution (half-normal distribution) with the mean of the underlying random variable being 0 [Eq. (4)],

$$NF_{FoldedNormal} = RN \cdot \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}}. \tag{7}$$

D. Statistical analysis

PCA was employed to assess the phase coherence of the CM_{h1} potential across various stimulation levels. This was achieved by observing the alignment of these complex potentials along the principal components. A high degree of phase coherence is indicated by a high coefficient of determination for a single principal component. Conversely, a spread in multiple directions signifies a low degree of phase coherence.

Levene’s tests were performed to statistically verify the consistency of the variances of the real and imaginary parts of the recorded CM_{h1} potentials across all stimulation levels. A p-value greater than 0.05 indicates no significant difference in variance across stimulation levels, supporting the assumption that the homogeneity of variance is met. The Levene’s tests were performed in MATLAB.

To verify the circularly symmetric normal distribution of the recorded potentials in the complex domain, the Henze-Zirkler test, Mardia’s tests, and the Anderson-Darling test were used. The Henze-Zirkler test was conducted to assess whether the real and imaginary parts of the recorded responses follow a bivariate normal distribution across subjects and stimulation levels. A p-value of the test

greater than 0.05 suggests that the data likely follows a bivariate normal distribution. Mardia’s tests were additionally conducted to evaluate the bivariate normality of the real and imaginary parts of the recorded responses in terms of skewness and kurtosis. A p-value greater than 0.05 for these tests suggests that the data likely follows a bivariate normal distribution. The Anderson-Darling Test was conducted to test the univariate normal distribution of real and imaginary part of the complex CM potentials. If the p-values exceed 0.05, it suggests that the data likely follows a univariate normal distribution. The p-values reported for the normality test were not adjusted for multiple comparisons, as this represents the most conservative approach. The Henze-Zirkler, Mardia, and Anderson-Darling tests were performed in R using the MVN package.

III. RESULTS

A. Amplitude growth

Figure 4 shows an example of the time series of the CM_{h1} potentials for study participant ID 9, recorded in response to 750 Hz acoustic pure tone stimuli presented at stimulation levels between 63 dB SPL (below psychoacoustic detection threshold) and 103 dB SPL (MCL). Based on the subject’s audiogram and in accordance with ISO 389-8:2004, the threshold of audibility for ID 9 at 750 Hz was determined to be 81 dB SPL. The waveforms already indicate phase coherence in the stimulus responses, which is independent of the stimulation level.

B. Phase coherence of cochlear potentials across stimulation level

Figure 5 (columns 1 and 2) shows amplitudes and phases for the CM_{h1} responses across stimulation levels for all study participants. The shown data are averaged from 120 ECoChG epochs (120 condensation and 120 rarefaction) each.

As shown in Fig. 5 (first column), and extensively characterized in Krüger *et al.* (2020a), the amplitude of CM_{h1} potentials mostly increased exponentially with increasing stimulation level. Moreover, it can be observed that the phase of the CM_{h1} potential appears to be coherent across stimulation levels (Fig. 5, second column). This phase coherence across stimulation levels is also evident in a good approximation through a PCA performed for the complex CM_{h1} Fourier coefficients obtained from ECoG recorded across stimulation levels (Table II). The PCA revealed a high coefficient of determination of 95.33% on average for the first principle component and a small coefficient of determination of 4.67% on average for the second principle component. The PCA showed that the vast majority of the total variance in the data is explained by the first principal component. This suggests a strong phase coherence across stimulation levels.

Figure 5 (column 3) shows the STD of the CM_{h1} phase as a function of the stimulation level. STD_{ϕ} was computed using Eq. (7), where N is the number of recordings (epochs), ϕ_n the phase of the n -th recording, and ϕ_{avg} the average phase angle obtained from the N recordings,

$$STD_{\phi} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{n=1}^N (\phi_n - \phi_{avg})^2}{N(N-1)}}. \quad (8)$$

Phase angles were determined as the arctan of the complex Fourier coefficient or the averaged complex Fourier coefficient corresponding to the stimulation frequency used to evoke the CM_{h1} .

It is shown that the STD_{ϕ} of CM_{h1} phases decreased as a function of the stimulation level or stimulus response amplitude (Fig. 5, third column). The observed decrease in STD can be attributed to the enhancement of the SNR, resulting from the increasing response amplitude due to higher stimulation levels. Consequently, the error in phase estimation decreased with increased stimulation level or SNR, respectively. As expected, it turns out that the accuracy of phase estimation improves with increasing stimulation levels due to the increase in SNR.

C. Noise of the CM potentials across stimulation level

The improvement of the SNR with increasing stimulation level can be explained by additive noise, as already mentioned in Krüger *et al.* (2020a). The assumption that CM_{h1} potentials are affected by additive noise can be confirmed by the constant variance of the real and imaginary components of the CM, regardless of the stimulation level (Fig. 6). Figure 6 shows the variance of the real and imaginary parts as well as the absolute deviation from the mean of the Fourier-transformed CM_{h1} response epochs as a function of the stimulation level. Even if there are differences in variance between the study participants, the variance within each study participant seems to be consistent across ECoG recordings and thus independent of the stimulation

level. This condition allows for the estimation of residual noise or the noise floor independently of the stimulation level or the amplitude of the stimulus response.

Levene's tests were performed to statistically verify the consistency of the deviation of the real and imaginary parts of the recorded CM_{h1} potentials across all stimulation levels. Levene's tests revealed no significant difference in deviation across stimulation levels for all study participants (Table III). The results show bivariate homoscedasticity across stimulation levels for all subjects, which is the reason why residual noise and a noise floor can be measured independently of stimulation level or receptor potential. Thus, no additional measurement is required to characterize the noise.

D. Circularly symmetric normal distribution

A normally distributed noise affecting the ECoG recordings (CM_{h1} responses) in the time domain leads to a circularly symmetric normal distribution in the complex domain. Figure 7 shows the density distribution of the recorded CM_{h1} responses across all subjects and stimulation levels. As can be observed, the density of the distribution is most concentrated at the center and symmetrically decreases with increasing distance, which suggests a circularly symmetric normal distribution. The results of the conducted Henze-Zirkler test, Mardia's tests, and the Anderson-

FIG. 4. Raw time series of the CM_{diff} potentials for subject ID 9 recorded in response to acoustic pure tone stimulation presented at various levels. Acoustic stimuli were presented at levels between 63 dB SPL (below psychoacoustic detection threshold) and 103 dB SPL (MCL).

FIG. 5. CM_{h1} amplitude and phase as a function of the stimulation level, and STD of the CM_{h1} amplitude as a function of the stimulation level. Each row shows the data from one study participant. The shown data are obtained from 120 ECoG epochs (120 condensation and 120 rarefaction) each.

Darling tests suggest that the recorded CM_{h1} responses follow a circularly symmetric normal distribution. The results of the Henze-Zirkler tests showed that only two of the overall 63 measurements were significant different from bivariate normality for all measurements across subjects and stimulation levels. The results of the Mardia's tests showed that 60 of the 63 measurements were not significantly different from a bivariate normal distribution in terms of skewness or kurtosis (ID 8 at 65 dB SPL, ID 9 at 63 dB SPL, and ID9 at 103 dB SPL). The supplementary Anderson-Darling tests conducted for the real and imaginary parts of the complex CM_{h1} responses revealed that across the majority of measurements, the results were statistically not significantly

different from a univariate normal distribution, which further supports the assumption of normality. Only five out of the 126 tests resulting from the real and imaginary parts of the 63 measurements showed a statistically significant deviation from the univariate normal distribution. A chi-square test [$\chi^2(1, N = 63) = 1.144, p = 0.285$] was conducted to determine if the number of CM_{h1} measurements deviating from the normal distribution significantly differed from the expected number. The null hypothesis was not rejected, indicating no significant difference from the expected number. This suggests that the population of measurements is normally distributed. In summary, both the univariate and bivariate normality of our data are supported by the results

TABLE II. PCA of complex CM_{h1} Fourier coefficients across stimulation levels. Phase difference ($\Delta\phi$) between the averaged phase of 120 CM_{h1} recorded in response to the max stimulation level used (usually MCL) and the phase obtained from the principal components (PCs) of the PCA.

ID	Coefficient of determination (%)		$\Delta\phi$	N
	1st PC	2nd PC		
1	81.29	18.71	7.74	600
2	93.26	6.74	4.81	480
3	99.87	0.13	0.65	840
4	82.79	17.21	51.2	480
5	99.96	0.04	0.43	1560
6	99.96	0.04	0.02	480
7	97.15	2.85	12.43	720
8	99.08	0.92	0.77	1200
9	99.99	0.01	0.14	600
10	99.98	0.02	0.49	600
Mean	95.33	4.67	7.87	756

of these statistical tests. The circularly symmetric normal distribution of CM responses in the complex domain confirms the presence of normally distributed additive noise in electrophysiological measurements. This behavior also explains the effectiveness of amplitude determination using phase information.

E. Noise floor estimation

Figure 8 shows the average noise floor and its STD of each study participant, estimated from ECochG recordings in response to AS at different levels. For each stimulation level, the noise floor can be derived from the residual noise according to Eqs. (6) and (7). The shown STD is calculated as the STD of the noise floors across individual stimulation levels for each study participant. The STD of the noise floor estimates based on absolute amplitudes obtained across stimulation levels was $0.0121 \mu\text{V}$ (max. STD = $0.0295 \mu\text{V}$ for ID08; min. STD = $0.0016 \mu\text{V}$ for ID02) when averaged across subjects. Noise floor estimates across stimulation levels based on phase-corrected absolute values of the real part of the complex numbers had a STD of $0.0077 \mu\text{V}$ (max. STD: $0.0188 \mu\text{V}$ for ID08; min. STD: $0.0010 \mu\text{V}$ for ID02) when averaged across study participants. A 36.33% decrease in the noise floor was obtained when considering the absolute real part compared to the absolute amplitudes of the CM_{h1} responses resulting in a decrease in $0.0457 \mu\text{V}$ for the measured study participants. The averaged noise floor across subjects derived from absolute amplitudes was $0.1258 \mu\text{V}$ (max = $0.1732 \mu\text{V}$; min = $0.0967 \mu\text{V}$; STD of means across subjects = $0.0292 \mu\text{V}$). The averaged noise floor across subjects derived from absolute values of the real part resulted in $0.0801 \mu\text{V}$ (max = $0.1102 \mu\text{V}$; min = $0.0616 \mu\text{V}$; STD of means across subjects = $0.0186 \mu\text{V}$). A Wilcoxon signed-rank test showed that noise floor levels obtained from absolute real values were significantly lower than those obtained from absolute amplitudes ($p = 0.002$, $z = 27$).

F. Amplitude estimation using phase coherence of CM potentials

Figure 9 shows simulated and measured CM_{h1} amplitude estimates as a function of the number of averages obtained without and with the use of reference phase information for three different stimulation levels. The left column of Fig. 9 shows simulated results of CM amplitude estimates. Simulations were performed to evaluate the benefits of phase coherence across the different stimulation levels with known amplitude and noise. For the simulations, CM amplitude obtained from averaged CM measurements ($N = 120$) were assumed to approximate well the amplitudes of the clean signals not affected by noise. A normally distributed noise with a STD obtained from the averaged CM measurements (120 recordings) was added to the CM amplitudes. For comparison, the STD of the noise as well as the used amplitude values were matched to the noise and the amplitudes obtained from real recordings. Averaging was performed to obtain response amplitudes as a function of the number of averages. A bootstrap method with 1000 iterations was used to determine mean values and STDs for each number of averages. The right column of Fig. 9 shows the corresponding measured CM_{h1} amplitudes obtained from ECochG recordings for subject ID 3. As with the simulations, a bootstrap method with 1000 iterations was used to determine the mean values and STDs for the respective number of averages for the recorded CM potentials. Both, simulations and measurements, show similar results.

As expected, CM_{h1} amplitudes with high SNRs yielded similar results, regardless of whether phase information was used (Fig. 9, first row). However, for smaller CM_{h1} potentials, amplitude estimates that do not make use of additional phase information are overestimated by the residual noise floor (Fig. 9, third row). In contrast, estimates obtained using additional phase information showed amplitudes below the noise floor for both, simulated and measured results. This discrepancy in amplitude estimates at low SNRs, derived from the two distinct methods, is attributed to the differences in their respective underlying probability density functions. A Wilcoxon signed-rank test indicated that there was a significant difference in CM_{h1} amplitudes obtained using absolute values and complex values ($p = 0.002$, $z = 27$). On average, amplitudes that use phase information were 16.5% below the amplitudes determined without phase information.

IV. DISCUSSION

In the current study, we analyzed acoustically evoked cochlear potentials of CI users with ipsilateral low-frequency residual hearing recorded through intracochlear electrodes. CM potentials derived as the difference response obtained from acoustic pure tone stimulation presented with alternating polarities were analyzed with respect to their phase coherence, variance, and density distribution functions. The analysis in the complex domain revealed phase coherence, consistent variance, as well as circularly

FIG. 6. Magnitudes of individual recordings from the mean-centered CM_{h1} responses for real and imaginary parts, as well as the magnitudes of the absolute values from the mean, as a function of the stimulation level for each subject. Mean-centering was performed by subtracting the mean of the CM_{h1} response from each data point, making the average of the CM_{h1} responses zero.

symmetric normal distribution of intracochlear recorded cochlear potentials across stimulation levels.

As a result of the consistent variance across stimulation levels, we showed the feasibility of residual and noise floor estimation from cochlear responses containing receptor potentials. Moreover, by utilizing the phase coherence

across stimulation levels, we introduce a novel method that uses phase information obtained from cochlear potentials recorded in response to high stimulation levels to improve amplitude estimates for cochlear potentials recorded in response to low stimulation levels. The effectiveness of the method is based on the circularly symmetric normal

TABLE III. Results of Levene’s tests conducted for the deviation of individual recordings from the mean-centered Fourier-transformed CM_{h1} responses for real and imaginary parts, as well as the deviation of the absolute values from the mean for all study participants. Mean-centering was performed by subtracting the mean of the CM_{h1} response from each data point, making the average of the CM_{h1} responses zero.

ID	Levene’s test					
	Real		Imag		Abs	
	f	p	f	p	f	p
1	1.5680	0.181	0.5289	0.715	1.0418	0.385
2	0.6532	0.581	0.8785	0.452	0.2452	0.865
3	0.2523	0.958	0.5651	0.758	0.97635	0.440
4	0.4250	0.735	1.6414	0.179	1.6283	0.182
5	0.1778	0.999	0.1367	0.9998	1.0617	0.389
6	1.4010	0.242	0.1295	0.943	0.39989	0.753
7	0.6793	0.639	0.7091	0.617	1.2806	0.270
8	1.1889	0.298	0.4977	0.877	0.52432	0.858
9	0.5542	0.696	0.0279	0.999	0.71727	0.580
10	0.4336	0.784	0.3098	0.872	0.070337	0.991

distribution of CM responses in the complex domain, which has been demonstrated across individual test subjects and stimulation levels.

We showed that the determination of CM amplitudes, based on the absolute magnitude for low amplitudes, is biased by the underlying Rician distribution. Utilizing knowledge about the phase of the response allowed us to apply the underlying folded normal distribution in the complex domain to reduce the bias in amplitude estimation. In comparison to the Rician distribution, we demonstrate that the folded normal distribution has a lower expected value for signals close to or below the noise floor. This significantly enhances the estimation of CM amplitudes at low stimulus intensities. We demonstrated that the noise floor could be significantly reduced with the inclusion of additional phase information. Additionally, we found that the estimates of the CM amplitude at low stimulation levels were significantly lower when additional phase information was used, compared to the estimation based on the absolute amplitude value ($p=0.002$). This suggests that the amplitude estimation using our proposed method is less biased by the noise in the recording.

These findings, the consistent variance, circularly symmetric normal distribution, as well as the phase coherence across stimulation levels, can have direct clinical applications as it could be used to reduce recording time by minimizing the number of required recordings or by improving the recording accuracy in terms of amplitude estimation of CM potentials obtained in response to low-intensity stimulation. For example, in previous studies behavioral thresholds were estimated from cochlear responses recorded at relatively high stimulation levels that were used to increase the response amplitude [e.g., Koka *et al.* (2017a) and Soulbey *et al.* (2021)]. Assuming a linear relation between AS levels in dB and CM amplitudes in dB, behavioral thresholds were

estimated by extrapolation. As shown in Krüger *et al.* (2020a), CM amplitudes can become saturated already at moderate stimulation levels, especially for subjects with relatively good residual hearing. Consequently, the quality of the threshold estimate depends not only on the SNR of the recording, but also on the respective stimulation level. Recording amplitude growth functions would be most appropriate to estimate behavioral thresholds from CMs (Soulbey *et al.*, 2021; Krüger *et al.*, 2020a). However, the process of recording at various stimulation levels is not only time-intensive but also not suitable for regular clinical practice (Krüger *et al.*, 2020a). The phase determined from a single recording with high SNR could be used to reduce the number of recordings for all subsequent measurements to determine the amplitude growth function. The advantage gained through knowledge of the phase is even stronger when the number of measurements is restricted. This is because the relative difference in the expected values of the Rice distribution and the folded normal distribution depends on the STD or the standard error of the measurement. With a reduction in measurements, the standard error or STD of the resulting measurement increases, consequently increasing the difference in the determined amplitude obtained by both methods (Figs. 3 and 9).

Estimates of residual noise or noise floor have been previously utilized to determine the significance of response amplitudes [e.g., Koka *et al.* (2017b) and Krüger *et al.* (2020b,a)], or to detect significant amplitude changes conducted under different stimulation conditions (Koka *et al.*, 2017b; Krüger *et al.*, 2020b,a). These noise estimates were typically obtained through supplementary measurements in the absence of any stimulation (Krüger *et al.*, 2020b,a) or by presupposing a constant noise level across subjects (Koka *et al.*, 2017a). As shown in the results of the current study, the noise in the CM recordings can vary across subjects. The finding in the current study that noise is consistent across stimulation levels provides the possibility to estimate residual noise and noise floor specific to each subject or recording condition without the need for additional measurements and without the need of assuming a constant noise floor across subjects. Moreover, the efficiency of noise estimation could be enhanced with respect to a single dedicated noise recording by averaging noise estimates derived from multiple recordings, for instance, in response to different stimulation intensities.

Despite the advantages of the method we have presented, it should be mentioned that there are some limitations. First, our method requires a phase estimation. Although this can be determined independently of stimulation level, if only one amplitude at low stimulation intensity is to be determined, an additional measurement for phase estimation is required. Second, the amplitude estimation depends on the accuracy of the phase estimation, which in turn depends on the SNR or the response amplitude. If a recording with a good SNR is not possible, improvement due to our method is limited. Furthermore, in the current study, we used the phase determined from the CM potentials

FIG. 7. Density distribution of complex CM_{h1} responses for all study participants and stimulation levels (dB SPL). For better visualization, the data were mean-centered. For this, the mean of the CM_{h1} response was subtracted from each data point, making the average of the CM_{h1} responses zero. Data are color-coded for better visualization of the density of data points in that area (yellow indicates high density, purple indicates low density of data points).

FIG. 8. Noise floor (NF) estimation and STD for all study participants, using the absolute values of the complex CM_{h1} responses and the absolute values of the real part of the phase-corrected CM_{h1} responses.

recorded in response to the highest stimulation levels, assuming the best SNR and the most accurate phase estimation. However, there is potential to improve this method by using alternative algorithms to further improve the accuracy and robustness of the phase estimation for implementation in a clinical setup. In addition to improving the phase estimation itself, methods that utilize phase information to enhance amplitude estimation can also be optimized. One promising approach is the use of half-wave rectification of the phase-corrected real part of complex potentials. This technique allows for a more accurate representation of the underlying signal, particularly at low SNRs, and reduces the bias compared to using the absolute value of the complex signal or the absolute value of the real part. Details of this approach are described in the [Appendix](#).

FIG. 9. Simulations and measurements of CM amplitudes as a function of number of averages without ($|Amplitude|$) and with ($|Real|$) the use of phase information for subject ID 3.

The findings of the current study may provide further evidence regarding the origin of intracochlear recorded ECoChG responses. The phase coherence across stimulation levels shows that the contribution of local and remote potentials does not change with stimulus intensity for intracochlear recorded ECoChG derived from apical electrodes of the CI. Similarly, it might also indicate that the proportion of hair cell (CM) and neuronal (ANN) sources in the recorded potentials does not change with the intensity of the stimulus. The absence of a change in phase with increasing stimulation intensity could be an indication that the potentials are sourced in close proximity to the recording electrodes. Generally, it is assumed that the phase (delay) of the CM potential behaves according to the traveling wave along the basilar membrane, and that the CM phase increases with increasing distance from the base of the cochlea. The contribution of the various anatomical or physiological origins of the recorded potentials may

depend on several other factors, including the relative location of the recording electrode. Dalbert *et al.* (2021) argued that signals recorded via intracochlear ECoChG are most likely dominated by the local or near-field contribution of cochlear potentials based on the results of several studies (Campbell *et al.*, 2017; Dalbert *et al.*, 2020; Giardina *et al.*, 2019; Giardina *et al.*, 2018). Conversely, the signals recorded via extracochlear electrodes are captured from potentials generated over a wider area in the base of the cochlea (far-field). Moreover, it has been shown that the latency of intracochlear recorded CMs evoked by low-frequency acoustic stimuli increased from base to apex if the recording electrode is moved from base to apex during insertion or if recorded after insertion across the electrodes of the array [e.g., Campbell *et al.* (2017)], which could be an indication of a near-field recording of cochlear potentials generated close to the location of the recording electrode.

The impact of stimulus intensity on the phase of acoustically evoked cochlear potentials has been investigated. Picton *et al.* (1977) studied the phase of CMs recorded from normal-hearing subjects using extracochlear surface electrodes. They noted a phase delay of 0.36 ms when acoustic stimuli of 60 and 30 dB SL intensities were presented. Based on their data, Picton *et al.* (1977) interpreted that the observed phase shift was caused by an increased contribution of CMs generated at the apex at lower intensities. Similarly, Zhang (2013) investigated the influence of stimulus intensity on the phase of acoustically evoked cochlear potentials in normal-hearing individuals using ear-canal electrodes. Although the phase difference of evoked potentials by Zhang (2013) was statistically not significant, a trend for a phase shift in CM responses was observed, similar to Picton *et al.* (1977).

The current study presents two major differences with respect to the studies by Picton *et al.* (1977) and Zhang (2013). First, ECochG recordings analyzed in the current study were derived via intracochlear electrodes, whereas ECochG recordings in Picton *et al.* (1977) and Zhang (2013) were derived through extracochlear ear-canal or scalp electrodes. Second, ECochG recordings analyzed by Picton *et al.* (1977) and Zhang (2013) were obtained from normal-hearing subjects, whereas ECochG recordings in the current study were derived from subjects with hearing loss, a condition that may alter cochlear mechanics, such as reducing the nonlinear amplification of the traveling wave. The absence of a phase delay with increasing stimulus intensity observed in our study contrasts with findings from previous research. This discrepancy may be due, at least in part, to differences in recording techniques. We used intracochlear recordings, which appear to be a relatively local or near-field measurement of cochlear potentials. Additionally, it has been shown that sensorineural hearing loss can affect the CM delay. For example, as reported by Campbell *et al.* (2017), the CM delay is reduced in subjects with sensorineural hearing loss [e.g., Eggermont (1979) and Campbell *et al.* (2017)]. This could also indicate that the results show locally recorded potentials.

V. CONCLUSION

In this study, we measured the phase coherence of CM potentials across AS levels recorded through the implanted electrodes of CI users with low-frequency ipsilateral residual hearing. Furthermore, we observed a consistent variance as well as a circularly symmetric normal distribution of the recorded potentials across stimulation levels in the complex domain. Based on these findings, we proposed a novel method for estimating residual noise and noise floor, independent of the receptor potential present in the recordings. Additionally, we introduced a new method that can be used to improve amplitude estimations of CM potentials, utilizing the phase coherence and the circularly symmetric normal distribution of the recorded potentials across stimulation levels.

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AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflicts to disclose.

Ethics Approval

The analyzed data were initially collected as part of the study by Krüger *et al.* (2020b,a). For that study, all subjects provided written informed consent to the study conditions, which were approved by the Institutional Review Board of the Hannover Medical School.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

APPENDIX: RECTIFIED NORMAL DISTRIBUTION AND ITS IMPLICATIONS FOR AMPLITUDE ESTIMATION

One way to further optimize the proposed method by utilizing the phase information of cochlear potentials is to apply half-wave rectification (HWR) to the phase-corrected real part of the complex potentials. In this context, HWR refers to setting all negative values to zero while keeping positive values unchanged. Similar to folding (i.e., full-wave rectification), HWR alters the probability density function of the signal. The resulting distribution is referred to as the rectified normal distribution. For a normally distributed random variable with a mean of $\mu = 0$, the expected value of the rectified normal distribution is given by

$$\mathbb{E}[\max(0, x)] = \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{2\pi}}. \tag{A1}$$

Here, \mathbb{E} is the expected value, and σ is the STD of the underlying normal distribution.

For an underlying normally distributed random variable with a mean of $\mu = 0$, the expected value (in this case the noise floor) derived from the rectified normal distribution is 50% lower than that from the folded normal distribution, and 68.2% lower than that from the Rice

FIG. 10. Advantages of half-wave rectification of phase-corrected real parts in complex potential analysis. (A) Circularly symmetric normal distribution and probability density functions for complex Fourier coefficients obtained from (CM_{h1}) responses. The probability density functions are derived from the Rician distribution (blue), the folded normal distribution (red), and the rectified normal distribution for stimulus response amplitudes an underlying complex normal random variable with a mean of $\mu = 0$ and a STD of 1. The inset illustrates the circularly symmetric normal distribution for complex Fourier coefficients obtained from (CM_{h1}) responses. The density of the normal distribution is color-coded from yellow (high density) to purple (low density). (B) Monte Carlo simulations comparing amplitude estimates (μV) of the simulated CM_{h1} response based on the Rice distribution, the folded normal distribution and the rectified normal distribution. The top panel shows the expected values of the three distributions as a function of the stimulus response amplitude, with the amplitude on the x axis representing the center of the underlying complex normal distribution ($\text{STD} = 1$). The middle panel displays the error of these estimates, defined as the difference between the expected values and the amplitude. The bottom panel illustrates the difference (ΔE) between amplitude estimates from the Rice distribution and the folded normal distribution as well as between the Rice distribution and the rectified normal distribution across various STDs (σ) of the underlying complex normal distribution. (C) Recorded CM amplitudes as a function of number of averages for subject ID 3. Amplitudes are obtained using absolute values of the complex potentials ($|\text{Amplitude}|$), absolute values of the phase-corrected real part of the complex potentials ($|\text{Real}|$) and obtained from the half-wave rectified phase-corrected real part of the complex potentials (Rectified Real).

distribution. Consequently, using HWR of the phase-corrected real part of recorded potentials allows for a further reduction in amplitude estimation bias at low SNRs, compared to using the absolute values of complex

potentials (Rice distribution) or the absolute values of the real part of complex potentials (folded normal distribution). According to the figures in the main manuscript the effect of rectification is illustrated in Fig. 10.

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